

Supplementary information

We provide an overview of the models used in our study. In what follows, $\mathcal{B}(\pi)$ denotes a Bernoulli distribution with parameter π and $\mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2)$ denotes a normal distribution with mean 0 and variance σ^2 and 1_{cond} denotes the indicator function equal to 1 if condition ‘*cond*’ is true, and 0 otherwise.

1 Continental model

1.1 Variables

Notation	Definition	Possible values
Y_{is}^c	Presence of a basal rot-hole on the tree i of forest s in the continental dataset	$\{0, 1\}$
d_{is}^c	DBH of the tree i of forest s in the continental dataset	$]0, +\infty[$
m_s	Management status of forest s in the continental dataset	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{'unmanaged'}, \\ \text{'managed'} \end{array} \right\}$

The response variable of the continental model is Y_{is}^c and d_{is}^c and m_s are used as covariates. The three variables constitute the continental dataset, denoted X^c .

1.2 Model

The continental model is defined as:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} Y_{is}^c \sim \mathcal{B}(\pi_{is}) \\ \pi_{is} = 1 - e^{-\left(\frac{d_{is}}{\lambda_s}\right)^k} \\ \log(\lambda_s) = \alpha + \beta \times 1_{m_s=\text{'managed'}} + \Delta_s \\ \Delta_s \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2) \\ k = e^\theta \end{array} \right. \quad (1)$$

where the parameters are :

Notation	Definition	Possible values
α	Intercept of the log scale in the basal rot-hole survival function	$] - \infty, +\infty [$
β	Effect of forest management on the log scale in the basal rot-hole survival function	$] - \infty, +\infty [$
σ^2	Variance of forest effect on the log scale in the basal rot-hole survival function	$]0, +\infty [$
θ	Log shape of the basal rot-hole survival function	$] - \infty, +\infty [$

1.3 Posterior distribution

The posterior distribution of parameters is $(\alpha, \beta, \sigma^2, \theta | X^c)$. From this posterior distribution, one can derive the posterior distribution of $(\mu, \theta | X^c)$, where μ is the log scale of survival function in a new managed forest, defined as :

$$\mu = \alpha + \beta + \sigma Z$$

with $Z \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$. The posterior distribution $(\mu, \theta | X^c)$ is used as an informative prior in the local model below.

2 Local model

2.1 Variables

Notation	Definition	Possible values
Y_{ip}^l	Presence of a basal rot-hole on the tree i of plot p in the Grésigne dataset	$\{0, 1\}$
d_{ip}^l	DBH of the tree i of plot p in the Grésigne dataset	$]0, +\infty[$
c_{ip}	Conversion status of the stand where tree i of plot p in the Grésigne dataset is located	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{'ended'} \\ \text{'ongoing'} \end{array} \right\}$

The response variable of the local model is Y_{ip}^l and d_{ip}^l and c_{ip} are used as covariates.

2.2 Model

The local model is defined as :

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} Y_{ip}^l \sim \mathcal{B}(\pi_{ip}) \\ \pi_{ip} = 1 - e^{-\left(\frac{d_{ip}}{\lambda_{ip}}\right)^l} \\ \log(\lambda_{ip}) = \gamma + \zeta 1_{c_{ip}=\text{'ongoing'}} + E_p \\ E_p \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \tau^2) \\ l = e^\kappa \end{array} \right. \quad (2)$$

where the parameters are :

Notation	Definition	Possible values
γ	Intercept of the log scale in the basal rot-hole survival function	$] -\infty, +\infty [$
ζ	Effect of stand conversion on the log scale in the basal rot-hole survival function	$] -\infty, +\infty [$
τ^2	Variance of the plot effect on the log scale in the basal rot-hole survival function	$] 0, +\infty [$
κ	Log shape of the basal rot-hole survival function	$] -\infty, +\infty [$

2.3 Potential identifiability issues

In this section, we consider a case of strong confounding effect of tree DBH and stand conversion status by assuming that the random plot effect can be neglected and that there is no variation of DBH within management modalities. In stands where conversion has ended (resp. is still ongoing), all trees have a DBH of d_e (resp. d_o) and the probability of harbouring a basal rot-hole would be identical for all tree, equal to π_e (resp. π_o). In this case, the model (2) implies that:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{cloglog}(\pi_e) &= e^\kappa (\log(d_e) - \gamma) \\ \text{cloglog}(\pi_o) &= e^\kappa (\log(d_o) - \gamma - \zeta) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where cloglog stands for the complementary log-log function : $\text{cloglog}(p) = \log(-\log(1-p))$. Then, $e^\kappa (\log(d_e) - \gamma)$ and $e^\kappa (\log(d_o) - \gamma - \zeta)$ being kept constant, varying γ , ζ and κ would not change the prediction of the local model. In other words, the model would not be identifiable.

In practice, when tree DBH and stand conversion status are confounded, tree DBH are not perfectly homogeneous within stands. The identifiability problem may thus not arise so drastically, but the thought experiment presented above suggests that obtaining a separate estimation of management modality and tree DBH effects may be challenging. Typically equation (3) suggests that a confounded effect between tree DBH and stand conversion status should generally render the region of parameters space defined by the following equations weakly identifiable :

$$\begin{aligned} \text{cloglog}(\hat{\pi}_e) &= e^\kappa (\log(\bar{d}_e) - \gamma) \\ \text{cloglog}(\hat{\pi}_o) &= e^\kappa (\log(\bar{d}_o) - \gamma - \zeta) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where $\hat{\pi}_e$ (resp. $\hat{\pi}_o$) is the empirical proportion of trees with a basal rot-hole within stands where conversion has ended (resp. where conversion is ongoing), and \bar{d}_e (resp. \bar{d}_o) is the average tree DBH within stands where conversion has ended (resp. where conversion is ongoing).

2.4 Priors

2.4.1 Setting independent priors on scale parameters

As explained in main text, prior distributions of γ (log scale parameter in stands where conversion has ended) and $\gamma + \zeta$ (log scale parameter in stands where conversion is ongoing) are set equal in the Bayesian estimation process. This is done by adjusting the prior distribution of ζ . First, we set the mean of ζ to $m(\zeta) = 0$, which ensures that $m(\gamma + \zeta) = m(\gamma)$, where $m(\cdot)$ designate the mean of prior distribution. Using that $v(\gamma + \zeta) = v(\gamma) + v(\zeta) + 2 \times c(\gamma, \zeta)$ — where $v(\cdot)$ and $c(\cdot, \cdot)$ are used for the variance and covariance of prior distributions — we set the covariance between ζ and γ priors to $c(\gamma, \zeta) = -V(\zeta)/2$, which ensures that $V(\gamma + \zeta) = V(\gamma)$. Because we had no *a priori* on the effect of conversion ζ , and noting that the prior of (γ, ζ) is well-defined only if $0 < V(\zeta) < 4V(\gamma)$, we set $V(\zeta)$ to a large but non-degenerated value by choosing $V(\zeta) = 3V(\gamma)$. We thus end up with the following specifications for ζ prior :

$$\begin{aligned} m(\zeta) &= 0 \\ v(\zeta) &= 3V(\gamma) \\ c(\zeta, \gamma) &= -1.5 \times V(\gamma) \end{aligned}$$

2.4.2 Defining informative priors from the continental model

Informative priors for the log scale parameter in stands where conversion has ended (γ), the effect of ongoing conversion on log scale parameter (ζ) and the log shape parameter (κ) are obtained from the posterior $(\mu, \theta|X^c)$ of the continental model:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \gamma \\ \zeta \\ \kappa \end{pmatrix} \sim \mathcal{N} \left(\begin{bmatrix} \mathbb{E}[\mu|X^c] \\ 0 \\ \mathbb{E}[\theta|X^c] \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} \mathbb{V}[\mu|X^c] & -\frac{3}{2}\mathbb{V}[\mu|X^c] & \mathbb{C}[\mu, \theta|X^c] \\ -\frac{3}{2}\mathbb{V}[\mu|X^c] & 3\mathbb{V}[\mu|X^c] & 0 \\ \mathbb{C}[\mu, \theta|X^c] & 0 & \mathbb{V}[\theta|X^c] \end{bmatrix} \right)$$

where:

- $\mathbb{E}[\mu|X^c]$ (resp. $\mathbb{E}[\theta|X^c]$) is the posterior mean of μ (resp. θ) in the continental model;
- $\mathbb{V}[\mu|X^c]$ (resp. $\mathbb{V}[\theta|X^c]$) is the posterior variance of μ (resp. θ) in the continental model;
- $\mathbb{C}[\mu, \theta|X^c]$ is the posterior covariance between μ and θ in the continental model.

The prior parameter τ^2 has a vague prior, set independently from the other parameters.